

Gender Biased Breastfeeding Practices: A Sociological Study Of Haryana

Paper Id : 19082 Submission Date : 2024-07-11 Acceptance Date : 2024-07-22 Publication Date : 2024-07-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13319373

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/resonance.php#8>

Vandana Kumari

Assistant Professor
Department Of Sociology
Kurukshetra University
Kurukshetra, Haryana,
India

Abstract

The initial age of the children most likely first 2 years very crucial for the children's overall development and growth. Any malnutrition throughout, the age of two years would have impact on the overall intellect and cognitive development. Every year, near about 5.6 million new-born die due to the non-satisfactory nutrition. The World Health Organization (WHO) recommends breast feeding should be at least six months. There is projected drop-infant mortality rate by 13% by introducing breast-feeding. As compared to non-exclusive breast-feeding there is a danger to the children by being dying due to diarrhoea and with the pneumonia having an age ranges from 0 to 5 months of the child which is increased two times. Particularly in rural India breast-feeding is related to the custom, beliefs of the community and sex of the child which influence it drastically, it is also affected by the communal, ethnic as well as the education of that particular area. Many factors which influence breastfeeding are woman's education, socio-economic status, demographic factors, traditions, employment, practices and religious beliefs etc. The important factors that influence breastfeeding are knowledge, attitude and practices about breastfeeding among newly mothers.

Keywords Gener, Biasness, Breastfeeding, Infants, Mortality, Health, Practices, Costume

Introduction India is a patriarchal country, and due to this system it affects health, education, employment, security, and socio-economic aspect related to women. Health is a most important aspect of life. Many study reveals that female malnutrition and gender biasness in health causes of patriarchy system and socio-cultural beliefs in India. Child mortality in India is higher among girls than boys. This contrasts with the rest of the world. The effects of malnutrition on girls are more severe in India as compared to boys. The girl child malnutrition in India is also a result of poor practice of breastfeeding adopted by mothers for girl child during lactation period and the food intake of adult women in households. India has the highest number of undernourished adult women among developing countries. These undernourished women give birth to undernourished children and if it is a girl child, it leads to further undernourishment among them. Study has also found that gender bias in health and nutrition starts appearing among Indian households as the boys reach the age of 15.

According to the 'Levels and Trends in Child Mortality' report by the United Nations Inter-agency group for child mortality, fewer nations showed gender disparities in child mortality, & across the world, on average, boys have a higher probability of dying before reaching age-5 than girls. But this trend wasn't reflected in India. India is among the few countries in the world where, the mortality under-5 years of girls, exceeded that of boys. This means that girls have a higher probability of dying before attaining the age of five years than boys. Through backward deduction, this means that effects of malnutrition are more pronounced for girls than boys. The root cause of such male-female differentials is the socio-cultural practices and mindset of the people which contribute to continued widespread prevalence of gender discrimination. Understandably, reducing the prevalence of malnutrition among girls holds the key to reducing the burden of female under-five deaths. Research shows that the girl child experiences mistreatment and neglect from the time of birth and thereafter during early childhood, facing a disadvantage in accessing nutrition and is thereby exposed to a higher risk of morbidity and mortality. Based on analysis of differential treatment of girls and boys in North India.

Traditional Trends Regarding Breastfeeding in Haryana

Many factors which influence breastfeeding are woman's education, socio-economic status, demographic factors, traditions, employment, practices and religious beliefs etc.

The important factors that influence breastfeeding are knowledge, attitude and practices about breastfeeding among newly mothers. Mothers obtain their knowledge and attitudes regarding breastfeeding from various sources like, articles, books, internet, social media, Anganbadi and Asha workers, elders, females of family and mother to mothers. There are many social, religious and cultural factors that influence the practice of breastfeeding. Most of the mothers waste their colostrum due to their beliefs, lack of knowledge and awareness about breastfeeding. They believe that it is no use to their infant. They give goat and cow milk and they also give sugar water, honey and Tea. In many cases mothers do not have the knowledge of benefits of breast milk. In many countries like India cultural, religious and social beliefs about breastfeeding are the major obstacles to infant feeding practices. As per the traditional social practices and beliefs that the breast milk is complete food that does not have any bad effect on the newborn's weight and height, resulted in mothers giving food and water to their newborn babies at too early an age. In Haryana about 75% of the newborns received their first feed on the third day after birth, which means that the infant is denied the benefits of colostrum of the first milk that remains in the breast of mother for nine months period of pregnancy and is thus harmful. In many cases, mothers are not aware of the importance of breast milk. The colostrums is discarded due to the general perception that it is heavy food and not suitable for the infant's health. Most of the mothers in Haryana deny the first milk because they follow the custom "Dudhidhulai" at child birth. It is the custom to call the father's sister to wash the breasts of the delivered women with milk before initiating breastfeeding. She is presented with silver, gold ornaments and some cash. This type of social custom about breastfeeding is the most significant barrier in infant feeding practices first milk that remains in the breast of mother for nine months period of pregnancy and is thus harmful. In many cases, mothers are not aware of the importance of breast milk. The colostrum is discarded due to the general perception that it is heavy food and not suitable for the infant's health.

Objective of study The purpose of the study to find out the 'Gender Biased Breastfeeding Practices: A Sociological Study of Haryana'.

Review of Literature Multiple studies have also shown that the predicament of women is more pronounced for low-income households with strong 'son' preferences and a greater prevalence of gender-bias. taboos, especially around menstruation and pregnancy are still very present, and many are quite harmful to women. Mahajan (1999) reported that 55% of mothers from areas fed colostrum to infant especially the male child as they considered it good for the baby. Statistically significant association was observed between this notion about colostrum with sex of the infant ($p > 0.05$) in India. Pre-lacteal feeding has been widely in practice since ancient times and appears to be widely prevalent among all sections whether rural or urban educated or uneducated mothers. Indian mothers feed on demand. Gender bias was reported in the feeding schedule of infants. Male infants were preferably fed on regimental feeding schedule then female infants. World Breastfeeding Week is held in the first week of August every year, supported by WHO, UNICEF and many Ministries of Health and civil society partners. The theme for 2024 is Closing the gap: Breastfeeding support for all. The campaign will celebrate breastfeeding mother's in all their diversity, throughout their breastfeeding journeys, while showcasing the ways families, societies, communities and health workers can have the back of every breastfeeding mother's.

Sampling

As a sample, 214 women who were to deliver the babies were selected by purposive selection techniques from four civil hospitals of Haryana state. On the basis of low female literacy rate of Haryana, four districts were selected. These were Mewat, Palwal, Fatehabad, and Sirsa. We have chosen civil hospital in selected district. Purposive Sampling technique was employed for the selection of the respondents who are to deliver babies and admit in maternity wards in selected civil hospitals.

A sample of 214 women between 18-35 years of age among these 214 women 41 from Mewat, 62 from Palwal, 53 from Fatehabad and 58 from Sirsa were included in each district. All the information was collected with the help of interview schedule. Primary data were analyzed with Statistical software SPSS. Therefore keeping in view the significance of the Breastfeeding the present study was carried out in the selected mothers. All the information is collected with the help of interview schedule. Primary data is analyzed with statistical software SPSS.

The information collected during the study is condensed and a code sheet is developed for the response to create the variables in the SPSS – Software (Version 20) for the purpose of statistical analysis and data validation. In order to examine the reliability and validity of the data, the Chi Square test is used for hypothesis testing. After that it is converted into tabular form and pie charts. Statistical tools like mean, percentage analysis were used to draw inferences.

Breast feed the infant soon after Birth

Breastfeeding the infant soon after birth	Frequency	Percent
FEMALE	86	40.2
MALE	128	59.8
Total	214	100.0

Above table reveals that 86 (40.2%) mothers of female infant breastfeed their infant soon after birth. On the other hand, 128 (59.8%) respondents breastfeed their male infant soon after birth. Majority of the mothers of male infant start breastfeed soon after birth.

Initiation Breast Feeding Start

First Feed Start		Frequency	Percent
First Day	Male	93	43.46
	Female	16	7.48
Second Day	Male	38	17.75
	Female	53	24.77
Third Day	Male	03	1.4
	Female	11	5.14
Total		214	100.0

The present study shows that 93 (43.46%) mothers of male infants started breastfeed on the first day of delivery .Only 16(7.48%) mothers of female infants started breastfeeding on first day after delivery . 38 (17.75%) mothers of male infants started breastfeeding on the second day of delivery and 53 (24.77%) mothers of female infants started breastfeeding on second day after delivery. Only 03(1.4%) started breastfeeding to their male infants on the third day of delivery and 11(5.14%) mothers of female infant started breastfeeding on third day of delivery. Present study show that respondents follow their family trends for initiation of breastfeeding on the bases of gender.

Duration of single feed

Duration		Frequency	Percent
5 Minutes	Male	01	0.47
	Female	00	0
10 Minutes	Male	09	4.21
	Female	23	10.75
15 Minutes	Male	19	8.88
	Female	35	16.35
20 Minutes	Male	85	39.71
	Female	42	19.63
Total		214	100.0

Above table depicts that only 42 (19.63%) respondents of female infants are breastfeed their infant continuously for up to 20 minutes. Majority of 85 (39.71%) mothers of male infants breast feed their infant for up to 20 minutes . This study shows that most of the mothers breastfeeding is biased on the basis of gender.

Breastfeeding demand schedule

Breastfeeding Schedule		Frequency	Percent
Yes	Male	102	47.67
	Female	47	21.96
	Male	22	10.28
No	Female	43	20.09
	214	100	100

The above table shows that most of the respondents 102(47.67%) of male infants are breastfeed their babies on demand only 47 (21.96%) respondents of female infants are breastfeed their infant on a fix schedule. One the other hand 22(10.28%) respondents of male infants and 43(20.09%) respondents of female infants are not follow demand of breastfeeding . This study reveals that most of the respondents of male infants are follow breastfeeding on demand to infants according to WHO recommendation . On the other hand most of the respondents of female infants are do not follow breastfeeding on demand to infants according to WHO recommendation

Provide breastmilk up to till 2 years

Provide breastmilk up to till 2 years		Frequency	Percent
Yes	Male	98	45.8
	Female	14	6.54
No	Male	28	13.08
	Female	74	34.58
Total		214	100.0

The above table shows that most of the respondents 102(47.67%) of male infants are breastfeed their babies on demand only 47 (21.96%) respondents of female infants are breastfeed their infant on a fix schedule. One the other hand 22(10.28%) respondents of male infants and 43(20.09%) respondents of female infants are not follow demand of breastfeeding . This study reveals that most of the respondents of male infants are follow breastfeeding on demand to infants according to WHO recommendation . On the other hand most of the respondents of female infants are do not follow breastfeeding on demand to infants according to WHO recommendation.

Taken balance diet during lactation period

Balance diet during lactation period		Frequency	Percent
Yes	Male	109	50.94
	Female	76	35.51
No	Male	10	4.67
	Female	19	8.88
Total		214	100.0

The study reveals that majority of 109 50.94 (%) respondents of male infants take balanced diet during lactation period. Only 76(35.51%) respondents of female infants take balanced diet during lactation period. Most of the mothers of male infants said that after gave birth of son, family members taken care of more and they given more nutritious food during lactation periods.

Over work load of household work interfere regular breastfeeding

Over work load interfere regard breastfeeding		Frequency	Percent
Yes	Male	11	5.14
	Female	45	21.03
No	Male	124	57.94
	Female	34	15.89
Total		214	100.0

The study reveals that most of the respondents of female infants 45 (21.03%) assume that over work load of house-hold work interferes the regular breastfeeding. Majority of the mothers of male infants 124 (57.949%) assume that over work load of household work does not interfere of regular breastfeeding. The study reveals that during over work load of household work does not any interfere regular breastfeeding for male infants .

Result and Discussion

The study reveals that 86 (40.2%) mothers of female infant breastfeed their infant soon after birth. On the other hand, 128 (59.8%) respondents breastfeed their male infant soon after birth. Majority of the mothers of male infant start breastfeed soon after birth. The present study shows that 93 (43.46%) mothers of male infants started breastfeed on the first day of delivery. Only 16(7.48%) mothers of female infants started breastfeeding on first day after delivery . 38 (17.75%) mothers of male infants started breastfeeding on the second day of delivery and 53 (24.77%) mothers of female infants started breastfeeding on second day after delivery. Only 03(1.4%) started breastfeeding to their male infants on

the third day of delivery and 11(5.14%) mothers of female infant started breastfeeding on third day of delivery. Present study show that respondents follow their family trends for initiation of breastfeeding on the bases of gender. The study depicts that only 42 (19.63%) respondents of female infants are breastfeed their infant continuously for up to 20 minutes. Majority of 85 (39.71%) mothers of male infant breast feed their infant for up to 20 minutes. This study shows that most of the mothers breastfeeding is biased on the basis of gender. The study shows that most of the respondents 102(47.67%) of male infants are breastfeed their babies on demand. only 47 (21.96%) respondents of female infants are breastfeed their infant on a fix schedule. One the other hand 22(10.28%) respondents of male infants and 43(20.09%) respondents of female infants are not follow demand of breastfeeding. This study reveals that most of the respondents of male infants are follow breastfeeding on demand to infants according to WHO recommendation . On the other hand most of the respondents of female infants are do not follow breastfeeding on demand to infants according to WHO recommendation. The study reveals that majority of 109 50.94 (%) respondents of male infants take balanced diet during lactation period. Only 76(35.51%) respondents of female infants take balanced diet during lactation period. Most of the mothers of male infants said that after gave birth of son, family members taken care of more and they given more nutritious food during lactation periods. The study show that most of the respondents of female infants 45 (21.03%) assume that over work load of house-hold work interferes the regular breastfeeding. Majority of the mothers of male infants 124 (57.949%) assume that over work load of household work does not interfere of regular breastfeeding. The study reveals that during over work load of household work does not any interfere regular breastfeeding for male infants.

Conclusion

Majority of the mothers of male infant start breastfeed soon after birth. Present study show that respondents follow their family trends for initiation of breastfeeding on the bases of gender. This study shows that most of the mothers breastfeeding is biased on the basis of gender This study reveals that most of the respondents of male infants are follow breastfeeding on demand to infants according to WHO recommendation. On the other hand most of the respondents of female infants are do not follow breastfeeding on demand to infants according to WHO recommendation. Most of the mothers of male infants said that after gave birth of son, family members taken care of more and they given more nutritious food during lactation period. The study reveals that during over work load of household work does not any interfere regular breastfeeding for male infants.

References

1. Agampodi SB, Agampodi TC, Udage K, Piyaseeli D. Breastfeeding practices in a public health field practice area in Sri Lanka: a survival analysis. *International Breastfeeding Journal* October 2007; 2:13
2. Diallo FB, Bell L, Moutquin JM, Garant MP. The effects of exclusive versus non-exclusive breastfeeding on specific infant morbidities in Conakry(Guinea). *Pan African Medical Journal* ISSN : 1937-8688.
3. <https://www.unicef.org/reports/levels-and-trends-child-mortality-report-2020>
4. <https://www.thehindubusinessline.com/opinion/a-gendered-view-of-indias-nutrition-strategy/article29433201.ece>
5. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0247065>
6. <https://feminisminindia.com/2020/06/26/gender-inequality-contributes-chronic-malnutrition-india/>
7. Jones G, Steketee R, Bhutta Z., Morris S and the Bellagio Child Survival Study Group. How many child deaths can we prevent this year? *Lancet* 2003; 362: 65-7
8. Kapil U and Manocha S (1990) Knowledge and attitude towards breast feeding among adolescent girls. *Ind J Pediatrics* 57: 401-404
9. Karnawat BS, Singh RN, Gupta BD and Choudry SP (1987) Knowledge and attitudes of hospital employees regarding infant feeding practices. *IndPediatr*24: 939-948.
10. Kemberling SR. Supporting breastfeeding. *Paediatrics* 1979, 63: 60-63
11. Khan TA, Ansari Z, Kidwani T and Malik A (1985) Maternal knowledge and belief of breast feeding. *IndPediatr*22 : 641-647.
12. Kimani-Murage EW, Madise NJ, Fotso JC, Kyubutungi C, Mutua MK, Gitau TM et al. Patterns and determinants of breastfeeding and complementary feeding practices in urban informal settlements, Nairobi Kenya, *BMC Public Health* 2011; 11:396
13. Mahajan Neeta (1999) A comparative study of Prevalin feeding practices among infants of both sexes. *Prachi-Journal of psychocultural dimensions* 15: 69-72.
14. Narayanan I, (1980) Breast feeding: a guide for practitioners and peripheral field personnel. *IndPediatrics*17: 531-1337
15. Narayanan I, (1980) Breast feeding: a guide for practitioners and peripheral field personnel. *IndPediatrics*17: 531-1337
16. Narayanan I, Puri RK, Dhanabalan M, Rao DC, Fernandez A and Balakrishnan

17. Narayanan I, Puri RK, Dhanabalan M, Rao DC, Fernandez A and Balakrishnan
18. National Family health Survey-2, (2000/2001) A report on breast feeding promotion in International Institute of population science. Bombay, [www.mahfw.nic.in/reports/01.pdf/part III ch 94-8 pdf](http://www.mahfw.nic.in/reports/01.pdf/part%20III%20ch%2094-8.pdf).
19. National Family health Survey-2, (2000/2001) A report on breast feeding promotion in International Institute of population science. Bombay, [www.mahfw.nic.in/reports/01.pdf/part III ch 94-8 pdf](http://www.mahfw.nic.in/reports/01.pdf/part%20III%20ch%2094-8.pdf).
20. S. (1974) some infant feeding and rearing practices in a rural community in Pondicherry. *Ind Pediatr* 11: 667-671.
21. S. (1974) some infant feeding and rearing practices in a rural community in Pondicherry. *Ind Pediatr* 11: 667-671.
22. Shalini C, Chakladar BK, Rao RSP, Infant feeding Knowledge and attitudes in a rural area Karnataka. *Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, 62: 707&712
23. World Health Organization. The optimal duration of exclusive breastfeeding: report of an expert consultation. Geneva: WHO, 2011
24. <https://www.who.int/campaigns/world-breastfeeding-week/2024>